

nf-core/proteinfold: a bioinformatics best-practice analysis pipeline for protein 3D structure prediction

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Abstract

The advances in deep learning frameworks have revolutionised protein studies and contributed to unprecedented accurate predictions of protein structures. The release of AlphaFold2 has materialised this major breakthrough. AlphaFold2 has also paved the way towards the development of a new generation of publicly available prediction tools whose combination constitutes a powerful toolkit for the systematic study of unknown proteomes. Despite their obvious usefulness, the deployment of these new methods across the research community remains hampered by technical hurdles. The main challenges are the dependency of each prediction method on a wealth of external software and sequence databases as well as the lack of a workflow framework that could orchestrate the execution of such tools in a scalable, portable and reproducible manner under well-defined standards. These issues can be specifically addressed by Nextflow together with the nf-core community initiative. Here we present nf-core/proteinfo (<https://github.com/nf-core/proteinfo>), a Nextflow pipeline developed according to nf-core guidelines, which simplifies the use of state-of-the-art techniques in protein structure modelling. These best-practice guidelines ensure that the pipeline is properly optimised for execution on the major cloud providers as well as HPC infrastructures. We foresee that this development endeavour will have a significant impact on a variety of biological analyses based on protein structures by granting access to an open-source, community-developed resource to obtain protein folds.

Introduction

In the last decades, major efforts have been dedicated to de novo prediction of protein structures (1–3). However, only recently novel tools such as AlphaFold2 (4) and subsequent developments such as ColabFold (5), have reached unprecedentedly accurate protein structure predictions by leveraging deep learning frameworks. These approaches mainly rely on evolutionary constraints on protein structures, which are subsequently used to train deep neural networks. Starting from a single protein sequence, such tools perform an extensive and computationally intensive search on genetic databases to identify homologous sequences and create a multiple sequence alignment (MSA). The obtained MSA, together with additional features extracted from publicly available template structures, are used as input for neural networks, which finally output the predicted conformations. Additionally, some of these tools can iteratively integrate their predictions as input for the neural network to refine the final results (4, 5).

Although these protein structure prediction tools have gained a lot of attention within the scientific community (6), their application remains challenging and limits their systematic exploitation. A complete prediction workflow requires orchestration of several steps and fetching of large databases so as to support the analysis at any scale. Limitations mainly arise from multiple dependencies on various software and database components. This constrains their portability across infrastructures and represents a major technical issue upon deployment. Moreover, these methods present multiple hardware requirements, as different steps require the use of different types of processor units and adequate matching of the computation with its optimal requirements. For example, executing on a GPU node tools that make no use of GPUs or TPUs, such as the database search and MSA computation, will solely lead to wasted computational resources without a gain in speed.

Workflow managers have become the standard solution to implement pipelines that adhere to computational best practices (7). Features incorporated into them, such as the native integration of container technologies, enable the deployment of the same pipeline into different computing environments without dealing with dependencies. Nextflow (8) is among the most widely used workflow managers and one of the reasons for its success is the nf-core project (9). The nf-core project is a community-based effort to collect Nextflow curated bioinformatics pipelines and to this end, it has established a set of standards to deliver reproducible, portable and interoperable data analyses pipelines.

Given the lack of any open-source pipeline for standardised deployment of protein structure prediction tools, which deals with the above-mentioned issues, we developed nf-core/proteinfold. nf-core/proteinfold is a best-practice pipeline for protein structure prediction implemented using the Nextflow workflow management system and that forms part of the nf-core community effort. Thanks to the adoption of the Nextflow framework architecture and the nf-core guidelines, the pipeline enables the parallel and independent execution of software components with varying hardware requirements to achieve the highest optimisation of computational resources. Furthermore, it supports the deployment of state-of-the-art protein structure modelling software across different infrastructures and guarantees reproducibility at the highest possible level through the execution of each tool within controlled and containerised computing environments.

Materials and Methods

nf-core/proteinfold is implemented in Nextflow DSL 2 syntax and is available on GitHub under <https://github.com/nf-core/proteinfold>.

The DSL 2 syntax extension supports the partitioning of the pipeline into independent and reusable units (modules). Additionally, it allows the definition of independent analysis segments (sub-workflows), which can be incorporated within multiple analyses (workflows). The availability of standalone units enhances the value of the resource, since each component stands as an autonomous resource, which can be integrated into external pipelines. Another obvious advantage of DSL 2 syntax is the minimisation of code duplication and increased code manageability.

The reproducibility of the workflow is ensured by the execution of each module within a controlled environment by employing containerisation technologies, such as Docker and Singularity. When available, each module is assigned to a single Biocontainers Docker and Singularity image (10), as required by the nf-core guidelines. In the remaining cases, where modules usually need a plethora of dependencies for their execution, an ad-hoc Docker image is created and made available through DockerHub. If Singularity is the specified container platform, this Docker image is automatically converted to its Singularity equivalent by Nextflow. Docker and Singularity images can be accessed and used outside of the context of the pipeline, thereby representing an independent resource.

nf-core/proteinfold is included within the nf-core community effort and, therefore, follows strict best-practice guidelines. First, the pipeline comes with extensive documentation of usage, parameters and results. Moreover, to ensure its quality and reliability, peer-reviews by at least 2 developers are carried out before each release. On top of this, a small-sized testing is used for continuous integration (CI) on GitHub so as to guarantee the full functionality of the pipeline upon development. Finally, to secure its scalability, nf-core/proteinfold is tested on AWS using a real-sized dataset. The corresponding results are available at <https://nf-co.re/proteinfold>.

Results

Pipeline overview

As illustrated in Fig. 1, the nf-core/proteinfold pipeline consists of two main workflows for the execution of AlphaFold2 (v2.2.4) and ColabFold (v1.2.0) protein structure prediction software. The entry point of the pipeline is a two-column comma-separated values (CSV) file that contains the identifiers and the paths to the fasta files of the query protein sequences. Given that each row of the input CSV file is considered a distinct run, the query sequences meant for an individual multimer prediction should be included in a single multi-fasta file.

Input check and database and model parameters preparation

The initial step of the pipeline consists of the validation of the format and the content of the input CSV file. In parallel, the pipeline, based on the selected mode of the prediction software and the type of inference (monomer or multimer), prepares all the required databases and model parameters. Specifically, the user has the option either to download these prerequisites a priori and provide the path to this data or to allow the pipeline to automatically fetch the databases and model parameters and prepare them for the following processes. The databases used by AlphaFold2 are BFD (<https://bfd.mmseqs.com/>) (4, 11, 12), MGnify (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metagenomics/>) (13), PDB70 (https://wwwuser.gwdg.de/~compbiol/data/hhsuite/databases/hhsuite_dbs/), PDB (<https://www.rcsb.org/>) (14, 15), Uniclust (<https://uniclust.mmseqs.com/>) (16), UniProt (<https://www.uniprot.org/>) (17) and UniRef90 (<https://www.uniprot.org/help/uniref>) (18), while the ones used by ColabFold are UniRef30 (<https://www.uniprot.org/help/uniref>) and ColabfoldDB (<https://colabfold.mmseqs.com/>).

MSA computation and structure inference

Following the database and parameters preparation, the pipeline proceeds to the main analysis, which involves the multiple sequence alignment (MSA) computation and the structure inference. During the first part of this analysis, the input sequences serve as queries to search for homologous sequences in the genetic databases and for template structures in the equivalent structure databases mentioned above. This is achieved by using optimised tools for database search, such as jackhmmer (19) and HHblits (20) for

AlphaFold2 and MMSeqs2 (21) for ColabFold. The resulting MSA, together with the retrieved template structures (if available), are the inputs of the two-stage AlphaFold neural network that predicts the five best final conformations, relying on the specified model parameters.

nf-core/proteinfold provides alternative modes for the optimal execution of the MSA computation and the structure inference steps depending on the available resources. The AlphaFold2 workflow includes two modes: (a) the standard one, in which both the MSA computation and the structure inference are integrated into the same process and (b) the AlphaFold2 split mode where these two steps are implemented in separate processes. The latter implementation provides the flexibility to use different types of nodes for each of the steps (i.e. CPUs for the MSA computation and GPUs for the structure inference). The ColabFold workflow has also two modes, but contrary to the AlphaFold2 workflow, the MSA computation and the structure inference steps are separated in both of them. The difference between the two modes here lies in the fact that, when using the local mode, the pipeline executes the MSA computation in the underlying system, whereas in the web server mode the MSA computation is carried out on an external server. The default server is set to be the one provided by the ColabFold team, but the pipeline also enables using any remote ColabFold web server. Besides the provided modes, the pipeline supports the customization of the AlphaFold2 and ColabFold tool arguments via dedicated pipeline parameters or a custom Nextflow configuration file.

Output and quality control report

All the results produced during the execution together with the metadata related to the pipeline are outputted to a directory specified by the user. This data includes (a) the downloaded databases and model parameters (to avoid downloading them in upcoming executions), (b) the computed MSAs, (c) the best five inferred structures per query sequence accompanied by their confidence and accuracy measures - predicted Local Distance Difference Test (IDDT) (4, 22) and predicted aligned error (PAE) (23), (d) the raw model outputs, computation times and execution trace. All this information is also summarised and visualised in the automatically created MultiQC (24) report which summarises quality control metrics (Fig. 2).

Discussion

The advent of highly accurate deep-learning-based protein structure modelling methods has triggered a new era in structural biology, enabling the inference of native-like conformations for most of the proteomes with unknown structures. To achieve the generation of such structural data in a reproducible and consistent way, scalable and standard workflows are needed. For this reason, we developed `nf-core/proteinfold`, a user-friendly best-practice pipeline for protein structure prediction as a consequence of adopting the `nf-core` guidelines. Besides its inherent advantages of portability, scalability and reproducibility due to the use of Nextflow and containers, `nf-core/proteinfold` facilitates automation, since it handles all the internal and external dependencies of the used tools, as well as flexibility with a variety of available run modes. Furthermore, it provides comprehensive documentation and strong community support.

Although the first release of the pipeline already includes two of the most accurate prediction tools, AlphaFold2 (4) and ColabFold (5), we envision the incorporation of other open-source software so as to enable an easy and straightforward way to execute them under a unified computational framework that enables its seamless benchmark. To this direction, we aim to provide more protein structure modelling methods to increase the range of protein targets covered by the pipeline. Recently published frameworks based on protein language models that claim accurate and much faster predictions for orphan and metagenomic proteins are such examples (25–27).

Data Availability

nf-core/proteinfold is available on GitHub (<https://github.com/nf-core/proteinfold>). It is released under the MIT licence. The data used to carry out the full tests on AWS derives from the CASP14 competition (<https://predictioncenter.org/casp14/targetlist.cgi>).

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A full list of members is available at <https://nf-co.re/community>.

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Tables and Figures

Fig. 1. Schematic representation of the `nf-core/proteinfold` pipeline (v.1.0.0).

a

b

c

Fig. 2. Visualisation of ColabFold results included in the MultiQC report of the nf-core/proteinfold pipeline for the T1024 target of the CASP14 competition. (a) Predicted IDDT (pIDDT) values per residue for the five best-ranked predicted structures. **(b)** Predicted Aligned Error (PAE) matrices for each of the five best-ranked predicted structures. **(c)** Sequence coverage and sequence identity (colour scheme) between the query sequence and each of the sequences in the input multiple sequence alignment as a function of the residue position.